

THE SITUATION AND PROBLEMS OF LIBRARIAN TRAINING IN THE REPUBLIC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8188339>

Abstract. From the early years of independence, great attention is being paid to the preservation, study and promotion of written monuments reflecting our centuries-old cultural and scientific achievements. It is known that libraries have been a center of spirituality and enlightenment for people since time immemorial, and the human race has always lived in search of books.

Keywords: Librarian, library, fund, storage, librarian profession, modern librarian, manager librarian.

INTRODUCTION

The first libraries appeared on the territory of Uzbekistan in the last centuries of the 1st millennium BC. These are the first libraries, kutub means "books" in Arabic, khana means "house" in Persian, that is, a place where books and documents are stored. The services of libraries and librarians are incomparable in the transmission of these documents from generation to generation. The profession of librarianship is one of the ancient professions, which has been an integral part of the intellectual and social development of mankind since ancient times, and has made an impressive contribution to the development of the country's culture. Since ancient times, our people have honored the book as a miracle life lesson. Spiritual thinking, a place of treasures - the library was treated with respect and attention, and this respect has been preserved even now.

MAIN PART

Today's modern librarian is a professional who can not only quickly find the book the reader needs, but also knows all the features of storing printed publications, provides information services to visitors and knows modern language well, and can manage information technologies.

In particular [2],

- the librarian should know the rules of creating catalogs;
- knowledge of special library computer programs;
- to be able to communicate with people;
- have a good memory;
- likes to read books;
- politeness, emotional stability, determination, attentiveness, precision;

- must have qualities such as organization, concentration, and patience.

A peculiarity of the library profession is that it is impossible to work without such employees, even in the age of technological progress. They skillfully use computers, office equipment and the Internet, create databases and electronic presentations. Due to these changes in the library profession, specialties related to the modern librarianship such as manager librarian, librarian-technologist and database administrator appeared. Important professional qualities of a librarian: high communication skills, politeness, emotional endurance, good memory. On a daily basis. Conducting reading conferences and literary evenings requires a librarian to have high speech, moral culture, oratory skills. Individual work with students requires the librarian's knowledge of psychology and pedagogy. This is a librarian-teacher, librarian-psychologist who conducts bibliotherapy classes. It was not for nothing that Lev Oshanin said in his poem: "Good doctors of the human heart." The peculiarity of the profession of a librarian is that it is impossible to work without such employees, even in the age of technological progress. No machine can yet replace an expert in science, art, and celebrity.

But, unfortunately, the salaries of such workers are low, and the demand for librarians in the labor market is low.

- The librarian selects and provides necessary books for reading at home or in the reading room;
 - to control the preservation of the library fund, to replenish it; ordering, buying new books;
 - processing of received literature; compilation of catalogs;
 - organization of literary conferences, thematic seminars, discussions and exhibitions of newspapers, magazines, books.

Today, librarians organize various information carriers, audio and video materials, e-mail, electronic catalogs, collective catalogs. They skillfully use computers, office equipment and the Internet, create databases and electronic presentations. Due to these changes in the librarian profession, specialties related to the modern librarian profession such as manager librarian, librarian-technologist and database administrator have appeared.

A librarian can be safely called an intermediary between a person and a book. Some people believe that this profession is very simple and does not require special skills. But they are wrong. Reading requires the ability of a specialist to analyze information and process a large part of it.

The fact that the "Best Librarian" competition is held every year shows that this profession is highly regarded. This competition, along with increasing the librarian's reputation, encourages professionals to self-improve and improve their skills [3].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that librarianship was considered an equally necessary field for all eras. For this reason, special attention has always been paid to the development of this sector and the solution of its personnel problems.

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